

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

InScoreAI: Collaborative Score Inpainting with Anticipatory Transformers

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Supervisor: Rafael Ramírez-Melendez

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Abstract

Collaborative music composition is the process by which multiple individuals contribute to the creation of a musical work. In this project, an interface is created to help composers create collaboratively and reach consensus through flexible symbolic music generation using Anticipatory Transformers. This model generates MIDI inside a specific fragment of music taking into account the previous and following tokens. The central and most important part of the project are musicians and composers, they've been the focus from the start to the development and evaluation. A preliminary survey for experienced musicians and composers was developed to extract important features for the interface, the evaluation consisted of three tasks, one where the interface was used without the AI tools, one with the AI tools and the last one using the collaborative mode with AI tools. Results show that AI assistance significantly reduces the compositional effort and improves self-efficacy in individual workflows, but diminishes perceived ownership. In collaborative settings, the system effectively resolves interpersonal friction through AI-mediated "idea bridging," fostering consensus and mutual understanding, sense of ownership is higher compared to an individual AI setting though it is still a concern for some participants based on long responses. Professional composers showed concerns about AI making composers "lazy" and the works simple and predictable, while nonprofessionals outlined educational potentials for music collaborative settings.

Keywords: Human computer interaction (HCI); Symbolic Music Generation; Transformer model; Collaborative music composition;

Chapter 1

Introduction

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into music composition has evolved from experimental algorithms to practical tools capable of generating multi-instrument scores. However, a significant gap persists between AI’s technical capabilities and its application in real-world creative workflows. Current collaborative music software (e.g., MuseScore, Dorico, Flat.io) supports notation editing and basic real-time collaboration but lacks embedded AI assistance. Conversely, AI-driven tools (e.g., MuseNet, Jukebox) excel in autonomous generation but struggle with user controllability and flexibility often producing outputs misaligned with human intent or requiring manual refinement.

Recent advances in music inpainting (e.g., Anticipatory Transformers) enable more nuanced human-AI co-creation, allowing composers to generate passages conditioned on existing motifs or accompaniment. However, these innovations are tested through individual Human-AI workflows. Collaborative environments, where musicians create over the same score, face unresolved challenges: interpersonal friction during “clash of ideas” uneven creative control and the cognitive load of reconciling divergent visions. Tools like “Cococo” demonstrate AI’s potential as a “steerable partner” for novices in individual settings, but these tools lack features for multi-user collaboration or professional notation editing. This highlights a gap: AI-assisted environments for collaborative composition.

This thesis addresses a core question: How does AI integration affect creative processes in individual versus collaborative music score editing environments?

Specifically, we investigate:

- Whether AI tools amplify or diminish the sense of creative expression, self-efficacy, engagement, completeness, uniqueness, ownership, collaboration with the system, musical coherence, control, comprehensibility of the tool and effort when used individually versus in a collaborative setting.
- How AI-mediated workflows can resolve interpersonal friction (e.g., conflicting ideas) in group settings.
- What do composers request for a collaborative app with AI assistance.

1.1 Significance and Motivation

As identified in the state of the art, there is plenty of work regarding collaborative music composition practices and individual Human-AI collaboration, but there is a lack of research on AI’s influence in collaborative music practices. There is also a lack of music applications that support score editing, AI tools, and real-time collaborative features. Finally, the “lack of control” problem (Human-AI) and “lack of consensus” problem (CSCW) motivated this work.

An early idea was developed as a way of addressing these two problems: When creators disagree (e.g., two sections of music), traditional tools offer no mediation beyond debate or compromise, slowing progress, and risking group cohesion. AI symbolic inpainting generation models could act as “idea bridges” between two musical ideas from two different composers. AI could generate multiple transition options between conflicting ideas, transforming idea blocks into a decision, creating a “common ground” from which composers could develop new ideas.

By integrating Anticipatory Transformers into real-time coediting environments, we can use AI to generate proposals during clashes, fostering collective decision-making

and allowing users to freely select or discard these AI proposals, ensuring both AI control and possible group consensus.

1.2 Contributions

This research designs, implements, and evaluates a web-based collaborative score editor powered by an Anticipatory Transformer model. The system’s contributions address critical gaps in both AI music generation and collaborative composition by:

- Retrieving preferred collaborative app features from a survey conducted by professional composers.
- Extending Anticipatory Transformers to generate multi-track MIDI segments dynamically.
- Enabling melody regeneration conditioned on accompaniment (e.g., regenerating a soprano line based on alto, baritone and bass voices).
- Deploying a web-based notation editor that allows multiple users to co-edit scores synchronously.
- Embedding AI “steering tools” into the Web editor for inpainting measures, generating alternatives, and visualizing changes in real time by deploying a pretrained Anticipatory Transformer through an API.

1.3 Objectives

The objectives of this thesis are to:

- Review state-of-the-art generative symbolic models and previous work on collaborative composition tools.
- Develop a survey for composers and extract preferred features for collaborative applications.

- Develop a Web Application for real-time collaborative composition with generative tools.
- Conduct experiments evaluating key AI and collaboration metrics.

1.4 Structure of the Report

Chapter 2 reviews the state of the art. It spans from Human-Human collaborative composition to AI-Human collaborative composition, proposing a bridge between them: Humans-AI collaboration or AISCW (AI Supported Collaborative Work). In our context, AI could assist various composers on a collaborative composition by proposing inpainted ideas.

Chapter 3 describes the followed methods: a preliminary survey for extracting preferred features for a collaborative music application, the design of this application, and three experiments designed for composers. Experiments are evaluated with the data extracted from a survey filled by the composers with metrics that rate the system, the use of AI and the collaboration.

Chapter 4 shows the results of the experiments and Chapter 5 ends the report with Discussion and Conclusions.

Chapter 2

State of the art

2.1 Introduction

Collaborative music composition is the process by which multiple individuals contribute to the creation of a musical work. Its possibilities have been greatly expanded by the use of technology: early networked music, tabletops, multi-surface devices, and web interfaces have been used to foster collaboration and interaction between artists. Modern AI music generation tools propose co-creation between a single user and AI, but there is a lack of proposals exploring the use of AI as an assistant of collaborative processes between humans leaving untapped potential for resolving coordination challenges identified in CSCW music research. This chapter covers the following topics: Human-Human Collaboration, AI-Human Collaboration, and a proposed bridge between them: Human collaboration assisted by AI.

2.2 Human-human collaborative composition

2.2.1 From co-creation to networks

The history of collaborative music composition spans from traditional co-writing partnerships to avant-garde experiments and technology-mediated composition, documentation of this history is beyond the thesis scope but some milestones will be

presented to give a bird's-eye view of the topic.

A well documented example is the collaboration between the experimental artists John Cage and David Tudor who worked with indeterminate scores. The performer had the freedom to define some musical parameters; Glover [1] considers this to be an example of collaborative musical practice.

Later on, The League of Automatic Music Composers, founded by Jim Horton, put emphasis on connections between musicians and the use of computers to define new social contexts of music, while the collective known as The Hub (1980s) pioneered computer-mediated social interactions in music through real-time data exchange between performers, creating emergent structures from decentralized decisions [2].

Barbosa [3], who delivered the first systematic taxonomy of computer-supported collaborative music systems, analyzed this and other early manifestations of networked music and introduced the “Shared Sonic Environment” concept via the latency-adaptive Public Sound Objects (PSOs) platform.

2.2.2 Collaborative Physical Interfaces

Tangible interfaces prioritized egalitarian participation through spatial interaction paradigms. Jam-O-Drum [4] used circular multitouch surfaces to enable non-hierarchical rhythmic collaboration, while the famous reacTable [5] mapped physical object positions to sound parameters, allowing simultaneous manipulation by multiple users. Multi-surface devices and smartphones have been used as a tool of music collaboration, showing that responsiveness and visual feedback is important for the user [6], and that real-time shaping of musical ideas fosters unexpected and experimental results [7]. These systems traded precision for accessibility, fostering “low-floor” engagement at the cost of limited expressive depth.

2.2.3 Collaborative Digital Interfaces

Regarding collaboration using technological interfaces for music composition, a system for collaborative music composition over the web was introduced in [8]. This

was one of the first collaborative tools for music and included logs of versions and voting. The development of shared virtual environments [9] and cloud-based file sharing [10] for music collaboration culminated in projects like DISSCO [11], a platform that integrates algorithmic composition, sound synthesis, and user input in real-time, enabling multiple participants—whether co-located or remote—to collaboratively create and modify musical compositions.

Another important line of research has been the notion of mutual engagement in creative collaborations [12] [13]. This area explores how engagement in music collaboration in a digital tool can be measured. They found that adding instructions that emphasize collaboration can lead to more engagement, which was identified through several factors (like proximity of contributions, mutual modification, and acknowledgment, mirroring, or transformation of others' inputs). Moreover, they found a critical challenge: participants reported a clash of ideas and a lack of communication channels. In this work, we will tackle this issue by introducing AI tools to create inpainting proposals in order to reach consensus.

Digital interfaces for music collaboration have been also tackled by the field of music education, with platforms enabling “a powerful route in for compositional thinking” [14]. Studies of online composition [15] revealed that some asynchronous workflows improve organization and time management.

Several studies have shown successful evaluation metrics for collaborative environments, especially the Creativity Support Index (CSI) [16], a psychometrically validated survey tool designed to evaluate how effectively a technology (e.g., software, digital tool) supports users in creative tasks, and a project by Burkhardt *et al.* [17], an evaluation of collaboration in tech-driven design (e.g., virtual environments) that emphasizes mixed-method frameworks blending quantitative metrics with qualitative insights.

2.2.4 Software Ecosystem Analysis

Sometimes, music software incorporates collaboration in the form of cloud syncing and file sharing, but it is rare to find real-time editing as being an essential part of it. The most notable music editing software, Muscore, Sibelius and Dorico, offer professional editing but lack real-time collaboration, although some plugins have been developed for this purpose [18].

Noteflight, Flat.io and Soundslice are web applications with collab support to some extent, but, as the already mentioned editing software, they lack AI tools for symbolic music generation. An exception of this is AIVA, an AI music generation assistant that invites the user to co-create tracks. Unfortunately, its input and visualization have the style of a DAW with piano roll, but it is not a score editing tool. In general, this tool seems to better fit music producers, not composers.

Table 1 shows how current musical software supports diverse collaboration capabilities, but often lacks AI assistance and real-time collaboration, and when it does, it lacks score edition.

Software	Collab Type	Notation Support	AI Features
Muscore	Cloud Sync (MuseLab Plugin for collaboration)	Professional	None
Dorico	Async file sharing	Professional	None
Sibelius	Cloud sync	Professional	None
Noteflight	Real-time web	Basic	None
Flat.io	Real-time web	Intermediate	None
Soundslice	Sharing by links	Basic	None
Staffpad	Async cloud	Handwriting	None
AIVA	None	DAW integration	Full AI generation

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Collaborative Music Software

2.3 Human-AI Music-Making

2.3.1 AI Music Generation

The taxonomy proposed by Zhu *et al.* [19] shows that AI-driven music generation systems can be grouped into three methodological families, each defined by the input representation and learning paradigm they employ.

1. **Parameter based models:** These systems treat music as an ordered sequence of symbolic parameters (notes, durations, dynamics, etc.) and generate new sequences by modeling the statistical or heuristic relationships among them.
 - Markov chains (e.g. MARKOV MELODY GENERATOR): transition matrices store the probability of one musical event following another; generation proceeds by sampling from the learned matrix.
 - Rule based systems (e.g. MUSICSCORE): expert defined harmonic and rhythmic constraints that delimit a search space where valid sequences are assembled.
 - Evolutionary algorithms (e.g. GENJAM): candidate sequences go through mutation and crossover and a fitness function guides selection across multiple generations.
 - Neural networks (e.g. MAGENTA, JUKEBOX, MUSENET): recurrent or Transformer architectures that learn long-range dependencies in large MIDI or raw audio corpora and autoregressively predict the next token.
2. **Prompt based (conditional) models:** A natural language or audio prompt conditions the model, providing music that is, ideally, aligned with the description (e.g. RIFFUSION, MUSICLM, MUSICGEN).
3. **Visual based models:** These approaches convert video or visual embeddings into an intermediate representation that conditions the music generator (e.g. CMT, FOLEY MUSIC).

They identified the next limitations in most of the AI music generation models:

- Limited Control: Some models, such as MUSENET, may not adhere strictly to user-specified instruments, leading to unexpected results.
- Data Dependency: Tools like JUKEBOX are limited by the diversity of their training datasets, affecting their ability to generate specific styles.

- **Computational Complexity:** Models like JUKEBOX can be resource-intensive, making them less accessible for users without high-performance computing resources or for live applications.
- **Quality of Output:** Generated music often requires manual fine-tuning, as the initial output may not meet user expectations.

These limitations reveal the challenges of achieving fully autonomous and creatively rich AI music generation.

AI Symbolic Music Generation

Recent research on AI-driven symbolic music generation has highlighted the complexity of automating the composition process. Early deep learning approaches have excelled at capturing short-range dependencies to produce realistic local musical patterns, yet have often struggled with long-range structure, style alignment, and limited creative potential [20]. These limitations could also arise from the lack of unified methods for evaluating model performance, making it difficult to assess whether generated music meets professional standards of originality and coherence.

Multiple studies advocate for collaborative approaches that foreground expressiveness and human-machine co-creation [21], this approaches often propose “music inpainting” solutions.

Music inpainting

Music inpainting addresses the completion of missing segments within a musical work, aligning closely with iterative human creative workflows. The task is to generate a musically coherent sequence that bridges the given past context with the future context.

Early methodologies proposed probabilistic sampling. Gibbs sampling, a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) technique, has been widely applied—notably in DeepBach for resampling notes/voices in Bach chorales. Similarly, Coconet (CNN-based)

was developed to complete partial scores, framing generation as iterative “rewriting”. These piano-roll models, however, were limited to fixed-length spans [21]. Extending this, Ippolito *et al.* [22] used Transformers for infilling missing MIDI performances via Gibbs sampling, enabling composers to iteratively rewrite or morph sections.

Learning expressive latent spaces has also enabled greater diversity and user interaction. Pati *et al.* [23] introduced InpaintNet (VAE-based), generating connecting bars between clips via learned latent trajectories, allowing contextual manipulation. Chen *et al.* [24] proposed Music SketchNet, incorporating user-specified pitch/rhythm constraints (“sketches”) to fill monophonic gaps. A key limitation of both bar-level VAEs was rigid alignment to measure boundaries.

Recent work overcomes fixed-span limitations. Chang *et al.* [25] leveraged XLNet for variable-length completion, introducing relative bar encoding for nuanced positional awareness. Guo *et al.* [26] developed a Transformer framework enhancing stylistic fidelity to original material through control tokens governing key, track density, track polyphony, tensile strain, bar cloud diameter, and track occupation. This granular control facilitates interactive collaboration.

Important technical advances in controlling symbolic outputs can be seen in works such as the Anticipatory Music Transformer, where this inpainting paradigm helps generate specific passages around user-defined anchors [27], and MIDI-GPT, which offers track-based conditional generation for comprehensive musical arrangements [28]. Finally, a recent model called NotaGen emphasizes training paradigms from large language models to improve musicality and user-controllable features [29], showing how domain-specific adaptation can refine structure and coherence in classical compositions.

2.3.2 Human-AI collaboration

Zhu, *et al.* [19] mention the interdisciplinary potential of collaboration between humans and machines. This Human-AI collaboration is research that most of the time focuses on interactivity, steerability and control.

Huang, *et al.* [30] emphasize the importance of developing AI tools with creative workflows in mind and incorporating existing musical practices. Creators see AI as a partner for ideation and exploration but emphasize maintaining control over the final product [31]. In the same lines, AI-steering tools were found to improve the sense of ownership in the users [32].

One of the most notable research efforts on AI-steering tools for Human-AI music creation is presented in [33]. The study introduces “Cococo”, a web-based music editor that integrates AI-steering tools to support iterative music composition and enhance collaboration. Their claim is that not as many studies have paid attention to the potential and limitations of co-creation with AI tools. Their approach is to provide a web interface where you can compose SATB chorales using a Deep Neural Network trained on Bach pieces. You can select what voice to generate and generated content appears as multiple alternatives you can audition and choose from, improving controllability over the final output.

In their user study with music novices, the tools helped participants feel more empowered and connected to the compositions, while fostering a positive perception of AI’s role in creative tasks. This user study was evaluated by asking the users to compose a piece using a non-steerable AI tool like “Bach Doodle” and then composing a piece using “Cococo”. Then the users filled a survey with 7-point Likert scale items regarding efficacy, engagement, effort, controllability and other useful items of Human-AI collaboration.

Based on the results extracted from analyzing and comparing those items from both tasks, we can observe that users benefited from:

- Increased sense of control, trust, and ownership of compositions.
- Improved ability to solve problematic areas, learn new musical structures, and explore AI’s limits.
- Enhanced self-efficacy, creativity, and engagement in the co-creation process.

Users saw the AI as a collaborative partner when steering tools were available. Some participants envisioned using AI with different roles for different tasks. Therefore, future interfaces could let users define their creative goal, adapting the AI's role accordingly. For fuzzy goals, the AI might automatically explore ideas; for clear goals, it could respond to specific requests. Steering tools thus offer not only control over direction but also the deliberate option to invite creativity and new possibilities by ceding control.

2.4 Bridging the gap: Human collaboration assisted by AI or AISCW

Later, “Cococo” was tested in a collaborative human-human environment as a possible way to ease social friction during creative tasks [34]. Users were much more comfortable judging and debating AI proposals than human proposals, allowing them to establish common ground and progress efficiently. The study revealed that the non-human identity of the AI acted as a psychological safety net: participants freely rejected AI ideas without fear of offending a collaborator, reducing interpersonal tension. In addition, AI offered multiple alternatives during creative disagreements, allowing teams to move away from a dead end toward a compromise.

The limitations of this study show that there is a lot of space for improvement:

1. Although “Cococo” facilitated collaboration, it was not originally designed for multi-human workflows.
2. Instead of making “Cococo” collaborative, they used the Google Remote Desktop extension, allowing one of the participants to access the screen of the other user. This makes them share the same view of the platform but lacks essential collaborative features like independent actions for each user and visual feedback of these actions.
3. Some of the participants indicated that the system turned humans from “composers” to “advisors” or “curators” of AI output.

4. Its Bach-inspired training data constrained stylistic diversity.

Despite these limitations, the study uncovers the potential of AI as social glue: by sharing starting points, accelerating progress through auto-completion, and reframing criticism as collaborative “problem solving with a third party”. They evaluated the experiments by conducting semi-structured interviews from which high-level categories and themes were extracted. In our consideration, this approach could be benefited by the 7-point Likert scale items proposed by [33].

A recent study carried out by Fu *et al.* [35] used already developed AI audio tools (e.g. Suno and MusicGen) to carry collaborative compositions with novice creators. Their findings indicate that AI in collaborative environments can be perceived as:

1. As a "team member", with creative responsibilities (e.g., lyric generation, melody composition).
2. As a technical assistant with mixing, mastering, or genre-specific expertise where novices lacked proficiency.
3. As a mechanical output generator, criticized for producing content lacking emotional depth.

Although these tools lowered entry barriers (enabling novices to create full songs in minutes), they introduced critical limitations:

1. AI outputs were often inflexible (e.g., uneditable WAV/MP3 files) and hard to refine and integrate with human-generated elements.
2. Participants emphasized over-reliance on AI risked creative identity. Some of the teams consciously limited the role of AI to preserve artistic agency.
3. Despite accelerating ideation, AI compressed the preparatory stage, causing “decision fatigue” during idea validation. Novices were overwhelmed by abundant low-quality options and they stick to “satisficing choices” due to limited domain knowledge.

The study identifies seven different stages of co-creation in their “Human-AI Co-Creation Stage Model”: Problem identification, Preparation, Idea generation, Idea selection and validation, Collaging, refining and integration and Outcome. In the Collaging stage, participants manually merged fragmented AI outputs into cohesive works, a process that lacks controllability and was described by the participants as time consuming.

For evaluating the study, they combined artifact analysis, semi-structured interviews, and embedded ethnography. Over a 10-week undergraduate capstone course, researchers systematically analyzed teams’ weekly process logs (e.g., ideation iterations, role assignments), creative outputs (draft lyrics, Spotify-published EPs), and collaborative platforms (Figma/Miro boards). In-depth interviews with 9 participants captured insights on workflow dynamics, perceived AI roles, and ownership challenges, song playback was used to stimulate reflection. All data were analyzed by thematic analysis, first coding emergent themes and then mapping the findings to the stage model, revealing critical deviations from it such as a compressed or in-existent preparation phase. This design captured behavioral dimensions (e.g., time spent editing AI outputs) and perceptual dimensions (e.g., self-efficacy shifts).

To the best of our knowledge, these are the most notable and recent studies on how AI can affect collaborative musical composition practices. This thesis is an invitation to explore this gap that could be called “Humans-AI Collaboration” or “AI Supported Collaborative Work (AISCW)”. By joining the findings of both Human-Human and AI-Human music composition, we can answer some of the identified limitations of AI models (lack of control and creativity) as well as evolve the field of collaborative music composition by utilizing AI as and assistant of collaborative processes.

Collaborative tools lack mechanisms to resolve the “clash of ideas” problem identified in [12], where participants struggle to reconcile divergent concepts without mediation. AI could act as a *decentralized mediator* through two key strategies:

Idea Bridging: A Transformer model trained in past and future context (inpainting) samples could generate transitional material between conflicting contributions,

similar to Cococo’s steering tools [33] but applied interpersonally.

Enhanced Controllability: The infilled part can be limited to a selection made by the users in real time, also a “temperature” type variable can be changed for the generation. Once generated, users can see various proposals, listen to them, and accept or reject them. In this way, AI generation is not imposed on users.

Current music software often lacks real-time collaboration and AI assistance, this gap could be filled by our proposed implementation that consists of:

- **Interface:** Web-based notation editor with AI steerable controls.
- **Model:** Anticipatory transformer [27].
- **Interaction with the model:** Measure inpainting.
- **Feedback:** Real-time engagement visuals inspired by [5] findings.

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Preliminary survey

A preliminary survey was conducted with 20 professional composers to identify key requirements and feature preferences for a collaborative AI-assisted composition web application. The survey was formed and sent via Google Forms. The participants represented diverse musical roles and most of them had years of experience in musical composition, as shown in Table 2. Distributions that sum up to more than 100% correspond to multiple answer questions.

Feature Rating

Participants rated 14 potential features on a 7-point Likert scale (1=low interest, 7=high interest). Table 3 shows the highest-rated features based on percentage of high-interest responses (≥ 5), median, and modal values.

Key findings include:

- **Real-time collaboration** was the highest priority (90% high interest)
- **AI assistance** was strongly preferred for technical tasks: Harmonization (65% high interest), Orchestration (70% high interest) and Melodic development (65% high interest).

Table 2: Participant demographics from the preliminary survey (N=20)

Characteristic	Distribution
Primary Role(s)	
Composer	85%
Performer	60%
Music Producer	55%
Sound Designer	45%
Music Educator	25%
Music Student	20%
Composition Frequency	
Daily	25%
Weekly	45%
Monthly	25%
Occasionally	5%
Years of Experience	
6+ years	60%
4 years	20%
5 years	5%
2 years	5%
Beginners	10%

Table 3: Top-rated application features (N=20)

Feature	Median	Mode	% ≥ 5	Skewness
Real-time collaborative editing	7.0	7	90%	-1.45
Commenting tools	6.5	7	90%	-1.74
Providing music theory sources	6.0	7	80%	-1.27
Version control/history	6.5	7	75%	-1.19
Group decision workflow	5.5	7	70%	-0.99

- **Process features** (consensus management, participation analytics) received moderate interest (50-60% high interest)

AI Implementation Preferences

Clear preferences emerged regarding AI implementation and are shown in Table 4, most notably AI suggestion presentation On-demand only (95%).

Table 4: AI implementation preferences (N=20)

Preference	Distribution
Suggestion presentation	
On-demand only	95%
Real-time during composition	15%
After completing section	5%
Input methods	
Note duration + mouse placement	65%
MIDI keyboard input	65%
Piano roll interface	20%
Symbol dragging	10%

Notable qualitative insights included:

- **Musical inpainting** for bridging sections was mentioned by one of the users though the survey didn't mention inpainting: "Something that could be of benefit is suggestions for linking two or more parts. For example, two people create two different sections of a score. Having an AI that could suggest various ways to connect these two parts could be interesting."
- **Melody development and harmonization:** "I think melody development and harmonization, or suggestions for portions where the composer is stuck, could be of use to many people. This could be expanded into rhythm as well."

Feature Selection

Based on survey results, the following features were prioritized for the initial implementation:

- Core features:
 - Real-time collaborative editing
 - MIDI + duration selection input
 - On-demand AI assistance

- Musical inpainting (section bridging) for harmonization & melodic development
- Future version candidates:
 - Advanced commenting/annotation system
 - Contextual music theory guidance
 - Version comparison analytics
 - Contribution tracking metrics

3.2 InScoreAI Architecture

Full code repository can be supplied by the author upon request. The future plan for the code, after the report is completed, is to release it open source using Apache License v2, contributing to the open source web notation editing environment.

3.2.1 Web architecture

Sheet Music Edition

While JavaScript libraries such as `abcjs` and `Vexflow` offer accessible solutions for rendering music notation in web applications, they present significant limitations for collaborative score editing:

- **Layout Constraints:** `Vexflow` requires manual positioning of notation elements, making dynamic re-layout challenging during collaborative edits. `abcjs` relies on ABC notation, which lacks semantic depth for advanced notation.
- **Edition Constraints:** Few or inexistent implementations of interactive selection and edition of score elements.

Verovio emerged as an optimal solution due to:

Figure 1: InScoreAI Architecture

- **Native MEI Processing:** Direct MEI-to-SVG conversion preserves rich semantic music data during edits.
- **Dynamic Layout Engine:** Automatic reformatting handles complex notation changes (e.g., added measures, clef changes).
- **Comprehensive Toolkit:** Built-in methods for rendering current page, precise timing data and dynamic reformatting.

Some of the functions used are:

```
tk.renderToSVG() // Renders MEI to SVG dynamically
```


Figure 2: Web Architecture

Figure 3: Web GUI

```
tk.getPageCount() // Handles pagination
tk.getTimeForElement() // Measure Timing
tk.renderToMIDI() // Midi generation
```

Measures were rendered as interactive SVG elements. Click handling leveraged

Verovio's *xml:id* to track selections (e.g., *selectedMeasureIds*). Start and end time of the elected measures to re-generate was extracted using Verovio's time-mapping (*tk.renderToTimemap()*).

Editing Workflow

MEI DOM Manipulation was done by directly modifying MEI XML using DOM-Parser to insert/delete notes/rests based on user/MIDI input:

```
const meiDoc = parser.parseFromString(originalMEI, "text/xml");
const noteElement = meiDoc.createElementNS(MEI_NS, 'note');
layerElement.appendChild(noteElement);
```

Verovio validated edits against musical rules (e.g., measure duration checks using time signature data from *scoreDef*) so users could not insert durations over the maximum duration of each measure.

The workflow is as follows:

1. User toggles edit mode with a button
2. User selects a measure to input new notes
3. User selects a note duration with the computer keys (1 for whole note, 2 for half note, 3 for quarter note, etc.)
4. User plays a note on their MIDI keyboard (received through the Web MIDI API)

Playback System

MIDI was generated via *tk.renderToMIDI()* and synchronized with Tone.js for audio playback. Visual feedback during playback used Verovio's *tk.getElementsAtTime()* to highlight active notes. Verovio-generated MIDI was decoded and scheduled using *Tone.Part*, with timing derived from Verovio's temporal data (*playbackOffset*). Users can play or stop playback of a selection of measures or the whole score.

Collaboration (PeerJS)

As stated in the official documentation “PeerJS wraps the browser’s WebRTC implementation to provide a complete, configurable, and easy-to-use peer-to-peer connection API. A peer can have a data or media stream connection with a remote peer.” Verovio’s MEI state was serialized and synced in real-time between peers. Full-state broadcasts included MEI data and edit history. In our application User A connects to User B via Peer ID, full state synchronization is active and both users see real-time updates for:

- Score changes
- AI proposals (red highlight of the range generated)

AI Proposal System

AI-generated MEI fragments (received from the Flask backend) were integrated using Verovio’s measure-replacement functions (`replaceMeasureInMEI()`).

The AI generation workflow is as follows:

1. User selects a group of measures
2. Clicks on harmonize, inpaint or change melody (harmonize will not change the soprano and change melody will not change alto, baritone and bass, inpainting will change all)
3. A “Generating proposal 1/2...” text gets displayed
4. Once the first proposal is generated it is displayed in the score, the notes are updated and the users can listen to it
5. A “Generating proposal 2/2...” text gets displayed, once the second proposal is generated a few buttons appear where the users can independently select accept, reject and listen to proposals

6. Once one user accepts a proposal (or rejects), the score gets updated for both users

The relationship with the API is as follows:

1. The web sends the MIDI of the selected region, the *start_time* and *end_time* of generation and the *top_p* (nucleus sampling parameter covered in the API section)
2. The API returns a new MusicXML file that gets rendered

Challenges and Solutions

Table 5 shows the different challenges and solutions faced during the development of the environment.

Area	Issue	Solution
SVG Re-rendering	Loss of user state (e.g., selected measures) during SVG regeneration	Persist measure IDs in <code>selectedMeasureIds</code> and re-apply CSS classes (<code>.highlighted</code>) after rendering
Real-Time Collaboration	Edit conflicts during concurrent operations	Operational transforms using versioned history stacks (<code>historyStack</code> , <code>redoStack</code>) with MEI diffing before broadcast
Performance Optimization	Latency from full-score re-rendering on edits	Selective SVG updates using measure-level targeting and Verovio’s partial layout methods

Table 5: Technical Challenges and Solutions in Web Implementation

3.2.2 API

Symbolic Generation

The first iteration of our AI symbolic generation used LLMs (Llama and GPT4o) in different environments (Autogen and CrewAI) to generate abc notation displayed on a web using abcjs. The quality of outputs varied considerably and the length

Figure 4: API Architecture

of the generations was not consistent enough (even using pydantic models). It also lacked future context, that is why we went for an inpainting model recommended by the researcher Valerio Velardo, the Anticipatory Transformer.

Anticipatory Transformers: The Anticipatory Transformer [27] leverages a decoder-only transformer with a context length of 1,024 tokens. We used the tokenization with best results shown in the original paper; the arrival-time encoding, which is done by representing events as (time, duration, note) triplets (vocab size: 27,512). This arrival-time encoding (3 tokens/event), enables context-free reordering for better sequence modeling.

The model’s key innovation is its *anticipation mechanism*, which interleaves:

- **Events:** Note onsets/offsets
- **Controls:** User-defined constraints (e.g., future melody)

During training, controls appear t seconds ahead of events ($t = 5s$ in the implementation), enabling the model to learn dependencies between current events and future constraints. The model was trained on the Lakh MIDI dataset (178,561 files) with time quantized to 10ms resolution, pitch (0–127), and duration (0–10s). Three

model sizes were evaluated: Small (128M parameters), Medium (360M), and Large (780M). During inference, *nucleus sampling* (top- p) is used for generation, sampling from tokens where cumulative probability $\leq p$ (default: $p = 0.95$).

Why using Anticipatory Transformers:

Anticipatory transformers offer robust pre-trained models with high quality outputs. You can select the exact range to generate and the conditioning tokens. It also has a nucleus sampling *top_p* hyperparameters users can interact with.

Implementation Enhancements: Two critical improvements were made to the original implementation:

- **Compound Instrument Tokens:** The initial code merged multi-track MIDIs (e.g., two piano tracks) into a single track. We introduced compound tokens combining (*program, channel*) using bit-shifting:

```
compound_instr = (instr << 4) | channel
```

This preserves instrument identity during tokenization and enables four-track separation during generation (e.g., piano, drums, bass, strings).

- **Metadata Recovery:** Time signatures and tempo data (previously discarded) are now extracted during preprocessing and reinjected into generated MIDI files. This maintains rhythmic/metrical integrity:

```
meta_track.append(mido.MetaMessage('set_tempo', tempo=original_tempo))
meta_track.append(mido.MetaMessage('time_signature', ...))
```

Key utilities include:

- `midi_to_compound()`: now preserves multi-track structure via compound tokens
- `events_to_midi()`: Reconstructs MIDI with metadata recovery

- Velocity/note validation: Ensures MIDI compliance (velocity $\in [0, 127]$, note $\in [0, 127]$)

The compound token fix turns the transformer from a single-track to a multi-track model, demonstrating that architectural adjustments can unlock new creative applications without retraining.

Music Transformation Agents: Three agents were coded to take advantage of the transformer for user-driven transformations. All agents follow a unified workflow:

1. **Preprocessing:**

- Convert input MIDI \rightarrow tokenized events via `midi_to_events()`
- Clip events to user-selected time range [*start_time*, *end_time*]

2. **Generation:**

- Conditioned on *history* (events before *start_time*) and *controls* (constraints)
- Generate tokens via nucleus sampling (*top_p*)

3. **Postprocessing:**

- Merge generated/anticipated events \rightarrow MIDI via `events_to_midi()`
- Inject recovered metadata and clamp invalid values (e.g., MIDI pitches $\in [0, 127]$)

Harmonization Agent: Generates accompaniment conditioned on a melody. Given input MIDI:

1. Extract melody (instrument 0) as controls
2. Generate accompaniment tokens:

```
accompaniment = generate(model, controls=melody)
```

3. Combine new accompaniment with original melody

Infilling Agent: Inpaints missing segments using future context.

1. Extract events after *end_time* as **anticipated** controls
2. Generate infill tokens conditioned on future:

```
infilling = generate(model, controls=anticipated)
```

3. Merge infill with original events before *start_time* and after *end_time*

Melody-Changing Agent: Regenerates a melody based on (and preserving) accompaniment:

1. Treat the accompaniment as *controls*
2. Generate new melody conditioned on accompaniment:

```
new_melody = generate(model, controls=accompaniment)
```

3. Combine new melody with original accompaniment

API Workflow

The Flask API exposes three endpoints: `/upload`, `/uploadinfill`, and `/uploadchangemelody`.

Each endpoint:

- Accepts a MIDI file and time range (*start_time*, *end_time*)
- Routes to the corresponding agent (*harmonizer*, *infiller*, *change_melody*)
- Converts output MIDI → MusicXML for web rendering:

```
musicxml_str = midi_to_musicxml(temp_midi_path)
return jsonify({"musicxml": musicxml_str})
```

3.2.3 Deployment

First we tried deploying the web and API on the Skynote server, but there were several space and memory issues. The API used the (resource heavy) Transformers and torch python libraries. We tried fixing it by:

- Clearing pip caches
- Using the lightest anticipatory model
- Installing only the CPU version of torch library

We solved this issue by:

- Deploying the web part using Netlify
- Deploying the API using Huggingface Spaces by making a docker container. The API is currently running on a 32 GB RAM server (0.03\$ per hour) and can be upgraded to a 15 GB RAM GPU server (0.4\$ per hour)

The app can be accessed by entering <https://inscoreai.netlify.app/>

The generation time now is 7 seconds per score measure and all the experiments were conducted using this deployment.

3.3 Experiments

Three experiments were designed to evaluate the collaborative AI-assisted composition app. 16 composers participated across 8 90-minute sessions, with sessions conducted via Google Meet. The author was present during the entire session, annotating feedback and issues, this represents approximately 24 hours of work time.

Participants were paired according to availability (coordinated via Doodle), and feedback was collected through observation and a post-experiment survey (Google Forms). Musical material (starting and ending segments of 5 measures each) were

distributed via WeTransfer. Participants without physical MIDI keyboards used virtual alternatives (MidiKeys for macOS and vmpk/loopMIDI for Windows). Technical problems arose when participants used VPNs, non-Chrome browsers, or mobile 4G network sharing, causing system instability.

3.3.1 Evaluation Survey

The post-experiments survey employed a 7-point Likert scale (1: strongly disagree; 7: strongly agree) to measure user experience, drawing metrics from established frameworks (e. g. Creative expression metric: Rate 1-7 your agreement with (“I was able to express my creative goals in the composition made”). Core metrics for experiments 1,2 and 3 included:

- Musical Coherence and Control from [32]
- Creative Expression, Self Efficacy, Engagement, Completeness, Uniqueness, Ownership, Collaboration with the system, Comprehensibility and Effort from [33]

The specific metrics from established frameworks for evaluating collaboration in experiment 3 were:

- Collaboration, Easiness of idea sharing and Idea tracking from [16]
- Fluidity of collaboration, Mutual understanding and Consensus reaching from [17]

3.3.2 Experiment 1. Individual composition without AI tools

Participants began by loading a starting 5 measure MusicXML file, adding four empty measures, and adding a 5 measure ending MusicXML file. The task was to manually fill the 4 empty measures via MIDI input without AI assistance. This baseline experiment evaluated individual composition without AI.

3.3.3 Experiment 2. Individual composition with AI tools

Replicating Experiment 1's structure, participants used the AI system to generate content for the four empty measures. The AI provided suggestions that users could accept, modify, or reject. This experiment assessed the impact of AI on individual composition.

3.3.4 Experiment 3. Collective composition with AI tools

Pairs of composers collaborated in real-time to complete the four empty measures using both MIDI input and AI tools. Partners shared ideas, negotiated AI-generated suggestions, and jointly finalized the composition. The experiment assessed the impact of AI on collaborative composition and consensus building.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Quantitative Analysis

Statistical elements (mean, median, mode, skewness) were extracted from the 7-point likert scale items. To analyze the quantitative measures, paired t-tests using Benjamani-Hochberg correction were conducted using a false discovery rate $Q = 0.05$, following the same analysis as [33].

4.1.1 Individual No-AI use findings

Key findings from quantitative analysis regarding an Individual No-AI setting show that:

- **Ownership** in an individual setting ($\mu = 5.62$) shows the highest results compared to both AI ($\mu = 3.31$, $p=0.006$) and AI-Collaborative settings ($\mu = 3.88$).
- **Effort** ($\mu = 4.94$) was significantly higher compared to AI-assisted individual work ($\mu = 2.56$, $p=0.004$).

4.1.2 AI use findings

Key findings from quantitative analysis regarding AI show that:

- **Ownership** significantly decreased when using AI individually ($\mu = 3.31$) compared to the individual No-AI task ($\mu = 5.62$, $p=0.006$).
- **Effort** reduced significantly in AI-assisted individual work ($\mu = 2.56$) compared to No-AI ($\mu = 4.94$, $p=0.004$).
- AI assistance improved **self-efficacy** ($\mu = 5.31$ vs No-AI $\mu = 4.69$, $p=0.027$) but showed no statistical significant effects on creative expression or uniqueness.

4.1.3 Collaboration findings

Key findings from quantitative analysis regarding collaboration show that:

- Sense of **Ownership** ($\mu = 3.88$) showed no significant improvement compared to AI-assisted individual work ($\mu = 3.31$, $p=0.357$) but remained lower than No-AI ($\mu = 5.62$).
- **Effort** ($\mu = 3.50$) showed no significant difference from AI-assisted individual work ($\mu = 2.56$, $p=0.293$) but remained lower than No-AI ($\mu = 4.94$).

Collaboration metrics (Table 9) shows strong results with median values ≥ 6 for all aspects except **Idea Tracking** (Med=5), suggesting this as an area for improvement. Collaboration and idea sharing share a Med=7.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis

Thematic analysis was conducted following the method of [33]. These key themes were extracted from the long responses of the survey:

- **AI Benefits:**
 - "Solved tasks faster" (P4)
 - "Avoided mental blocks" (P7, P10)

- "Provided harmonization ideas" (P2)

- **AI Concerns:**

- "That people stop actively composing and will just let the AI compose for them"(P7)
- "Over predictable and non experimental or new music"(P10,P11)

- **Usability Concerns:**

- "Note input needs improvement" (P4, P7, P10)
- "Cannot edit single notes" (P2, P4)
- "Lack of MIDI feedback" (P1)

- **Educational Value:**

- "I think it could be very useful to motivate music students who are starting to create melodies or harmonies. It helps them see how their first exercises can become full musical pieces." (P4)
- Regarding the benefits of a collaborative platform: "I see a lot of benefits, for instance educational apps" (P10)

- **Collaboration Experience:**

- "I think the integration and design makes really easy to compose collaboratively and remotely." (P1)
- "It is easier to collaborate with other people by using this composition app (P3)"

4.2.1 Effect of Years of Experience

Participant data was split into two groups: professional (≥ 5 years, $n=8$) and non-professional (≤ 4 years, $n=8$)

Quantitative Differences: As shown in Figure 7, experienced composers reported a lower ownership, effort, and uniqueness sense in Experiment 1 (Individual) and lower uniqueness in Experiment 3 (Collaborative).

Qualitative Themes from Open-Ended Responses: Experienced composers were more concerned about "soulless/simple/predictable music"(P2, P6) and over-reliance on AI (e.g., "People will stop actively composing and just let the AI work". Less Experienced Composers praised AI for "avoiding mental blocks" (P3) (e.g., "I am not an expert in harmony, AI helped me to create the middle voices, at least as a starting point" (P5).

4.3 Tables and graphics

Figure 5: Mean values of items per experiment

Figure 6: Mean values of collaborative items in Experiment 3

Figure 7: Highest difference of mean values of items per group (Non-professional: experience of ≤ 4 years, Professional: ≥ 5 years)

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for Core Metrics (N=16)

Metric	Exp 1: Without AI				Exp 2: With AI				Exp 3: Collaborative			
	Mean	Med	Mode	Skew	Mean	Med	Mode	Skew	Mean	Med	Mode	Skew
Creative Expression	4.69	5.0	4	-0.47	4.50	5.0	5	-0.80	4.81	5.0	6	-0.71
Self-Efficacy	4.69	4.5	4	-0.06	5.31	5.0	7	-0.16	5.25	6.0	6	-0.62
Engagement	5.00	5.0	5	-1.46	5.81	6.0	5	0.35	5.88	6.0	6	-0.35
Completeness	5.00	5.5	6	-0.80	5.13	5.0	4	-0.22	5.69	6.0	7	-0.93
Uniqueness	4.00	3.5	3	0.18	3.81	4.0	4	0.62	4.50	5.0	6	-0.36
Ownership	5.62	6.5	7	-1.20	3.31	3.0	4	0.80	3.88	4.0	4	-0.24
Collaboration w/ System	5.31	6.0	7	-0.98	5.13	5.0	5	-0.23	5.75	6.0	6	-0.94
Musical Coherence	5.75	6.0	7	-0.60	5.62	5.0	5	0.42	5.94	6.0	6	-0.39
Control	5.50	6.0	7	-1.01	4.56	4.0	4	-0.11	4.75	5.0	6	-0.14
Comprehensibility	5.69	6.0	7	-1.04	6.06	6.0	7	-0.12	6.31	7.0	7	-1.76
Effort	4.94	6.0	6	-1.26	2.56	2.0	1	1.16	3.50	3.0	3	0.23

Table 7: Raw p-values for Experimental Comparisons (Uncorrected) $Q= 0.05$

Metric	Exp1 vs Exp2		Exp2 vs Exp3	
	p-value	Sig.	p-value	Sig.
Creative Expression	0.383		0.206	
Self-Efficacy	0.007	✓	0.774	
Engagement	0.003	✓	0.751	✓
Completeness	0.708		0.034	
Uniqueness	0.580		0.052	
Ownership	0,001	✓	0.227	
Collaboration w/ System	0.718		0.126	
Musical Coherence	0.652		0.055	
Control	0.083		0.606	
Comprehensibility	0.211		0.299	
Effort	0.001	✓	0.027	✓

Table 8: Inferential Statistics (Benjamini-Hochberg Corrected) $Q= 0.05$

Metric	Exp1 vs Exp2		Exp2 vs Exp3	
	p-value	Sig.	p-value	Sig.
Creative expression	0,602		0.378	
Self-Efficacy	0,027	✓	0,774	
Engagement	0,089		0.826	
Completeness	0,779		0,186	
Uniqueness	0,798		0.190	
Ownership	0,006	✓	0,357	
Collaboration w/ System	0,718		0.278	
Musical Coherence	0,797		0.153	
Control	0,181		0.740	
Comprehensibility	0,386		0.412	
Effort	0,004	✓	0,293	

Table 9: Collaboration Metrics in Exp 3 (N=16)

Metric	Mean	Median
Collaboration	6.19	7
Fluidity	6.13	6.5
Idea Sharing	6.31	7
Idea Tracking	5.25	5
Mutual Understanding	6.19	6
Consensus	6.38	6

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

Results confirm that AI integration distinctly reshapes creative processes across individual and collaborative environments, directly addressing our core research questions:

1. Measured metrics (Individual vs. Collaborative):

- Individual Use: AI drastically reduced effort ($\mu = 2.56$ vs. $\mu = 4.94$, $p=0.004$) and boosted self-efficacy ($\mu = 5.31$ vs. $\mu = 4.69$, $p=0.027$), corroborating studies on AI-steering tools [32],[33]. However, ownership declined significantly ($\mu = 3.31$ vs. $\mu = 5.62$, $p=0.006$), echoing fears of "soulless" outputs and over-reliance [31],[35].
- Collaborative Use: Ownership remained low ($\mu = 3.88$) and statistically indistinguishable from individual AI use ($p=0.357$), suggesting AI's role as a generator rather than co-author dilutes ownership regardless of context. Yet, collaboration metrics (e.g., Consensus, Med=6) exceeded expectations, indicating AI mitigates creative bottlenecks without resolving ownership trade-offs.

2. Resolving Interpersonal Friction:

High fluidity (Med=6.19) and consensus scores (Med=6.38) could suggest the efficacy of AI as "social glue" though qualitative critiques noted AI predictability could harness experimentation (P10, P11). Qualitative responses show that "We agreed fast and easy on which part to do" (P14). The author noted a varied set of approaches from the participants: dividing the composition in voices, in measures, using the AI to generate something while they were working on another part and re-harmonizing sections once they were finished.

3. **Composer Requirements:** Surveyed composers demanded real-time collaboration (90% voted ≥ 5), AI-aided technical tasks (e.g., harmonization: 65%), and "idea bridging" was mentioned in the qualitative responses. Our implementation addressed these via anticipatory transformers for multi-track inpainting and measure-level regeneration (features absent in state of the art software analyzed in Table 1).

Our findings extend the "steerable AI" paradigm to collaborative settings, confirming that AI enhances co-creation efficacy but complicates ownership. Unlike Cococo [33], which elevated novice ownership via constrained AI roles, our professional cohort perceived AI as a substitutive force, urging designs that preserve human agency.

5.1.1 Contributions

The contributions of this work are as follows:

Anticipatory Transformers can now:

- Generate multitrack MIDIs.
- Be used in a new manner (Melody change, conditioned on accompaniment).
- Be visualized in a web interface.
- Be visualized collaboratively in real-time.

A fully functional collaborative score editing + AI full-stack web app was designed and deployed. Composers now have a new tool to resolve:

- Clash of ideas. (A problem identified in the state of th art of Human-Human Collaboration)
- Lack of control with AI. (A problem identified in the state of the art of Human-AI Collaboration)

Finally: insightful feedback from 20 professional composers on ideal features for future collaborative applications was extracted. Also, long answers from the final survey reveal some possible educational potentials of collaborative apps.

5.1.2 Future steps

Web future steps

As mentioned above, the preliminary survey revealed several features that can be implemented in the future (they were not implemented due to time constraints). These features are: a commenting/annotation system, contextual music theory guidance, version comparison analytics (or full version control) and contribution tracking metrics. Some of this would be aligned with the improvement of the **Idea tracking** metric, which, as we mentioned, was the lowest. Other features we suggest are user log-in and note-level generation inside the interface.

Ideally a new open source score editing library for the web should be developed but, if this is not possible due to time and resources, the author suggests (for a production ready application) either contacting with the Noteflight team for the use of their notation editor or developing a plugin for MuseScore and keeping the web for visualization, AI, and version control.

API future steps

Future steps in the API could be focused on self-hosting the API on a powerful server.

The anticipatory transformer could be fine-tuned to fit the desired genre of the composers for more rich details. One (not yet tested) implementation of LLMs into

this application would be generating abc notation through natural language queries, turning this notation into MIDI and condition the anticipatory transformer on this MIDI.

The researcher Dimitry Bogdanov proposed using embeddings from both composers corpus of works (these could be imported in the app, though privacy issues should be taken into account) so the inpainting would be more aligned to a mix of their style, resulting in a possible improvement of consensus.

5.1.3 Limitations

Ideally, this application should be tested on more participants (now N=16), which was not possible due to the nature of the requirements set:

- Professional composers
- Proficient in score reading and editing
- Access to a Midi keyboard (physical or digital)

This N size is why some metric values should not be taken as a trend and generalization of the results cannot be taken for granted. The reason behind this was to focus on a specific population and perform long and exhaustive experiments where the author could be present for the whole time annotating feedback to extract developed insights and not short Yes/No answers. Thus, due to time constraints, this could not be done with a higher number of participants.

Time constraints also lead to a discard of other quantitative analysis as analyzing the MIDI files generated by the users (by analyzing repetitiveness, complexity, etc.) and then comparing AI and no-AI files in a focus group to see if there are perceptual differences.

The limited computational resources of the API also led to using the small version of the Anticipatory Transformer model on the experiments, limiting the quality of the output (which can even be higher).

5.2 Conclusions

This thesis addressed a critical gap in the intersection of artificial intelligence and collaborative creative practices by designing, implementing, and evaluating InScoreAI, a web-based platform integrating anticipatory transformers for real-time, AI-assisted collaborative music composition. Our work bridges the domains of Computer Supported Collaborative Work (CSCW) and Human-AI co-creation, proposing a novel paradigm: AI-Supported Collaborative Work (AISCW) for music. Through empirical studies with professional composers, we address our core research questions and show the potential (and challenges) of AI mediation in creative workflows.

AI significantly reduced compositional effort and enhanced self-efficacy, validating AI's role as a powerful technical assistant that accelerates workflow and overcomes creative blocks. However, this comes at the cost of a significant reduction in perceived ownership, raising concerns about over-reliance and "soulless" outputs among professional composers.

AI serves as an effective "social glue", demonstrably mitigating interpersonal friction during clashes of ideas. High median scores for Fluidity, Consensus, and Collaboration confirm that AI-generated "idea bridges" facilitate mutual understanding and efficient compromise. Although ownership remained low and comparable to individual AI use, the collaborative context fostered a marginally higher sense of shared ownership compared to solitary AI assistance, suggesting that collaboration partially mitigates the lack of sense of ownership.

We successfully extended anticipatory transformers with multi-track capabilities and embedded it within a collaborative web editor. Key technical contributions include compound instrument tokens preserving multi-track structure during generation, metadata recovery (tempo, time signatures) ensuring rhythmic/metrical integrity, and three "steering" agents (Harmonization, Inpainting and Melody-Changing) offering flexible, user-controllable AI interventions conditioned on melody, accompaniment or future context. This provides a robust solution to the "lack of control" problem prevalent in autonomous AI music generators.

InScoreAI effectively addresses the “lack of consensus” challenge identified in CSCW music research. By generating multiple transitional options (“idea bridges”) between conflicting human contributions and allowing real-time, independent audition/selection/rejection of proposals where AI acts as a neutral mediator. This transforms creative disagreements into collaborative problem-solving exercises focused on evaluating AI suggestions, thereby reducing interpersonal tension and accelerating progress toward shared goals.

The system directly addresses the high-priority features identified by professional composers: real-time collaboration (90% high interest), AI assistance for technical tasks (Harmonization and Melodic Development, 65%), and the requested "idea bridging" functionality. However, qualitative feedback by professional composers raised concerns about AI potentially fostering creative laziness, simplifying musical output, and diminishing the perceived uniqueness and experimental nature of compositions. Qualitative insights highlight the significant educational value of AI-assisted collaborative platforms, particularly for novice composers and students. Benefits include overcoming initial technical hurdles (e.g., harmonization), visualizing compositional possibilities, and motivating engagement by transforming exercises into fuller musical pieces within a supportive collaborative environment.

This thesis demonstrates that anticipatory transformers, integrated as steerable partners within a real-time collaborative environment, offer a powerful paradigm (AISCW) for transforming music composition. InScoreAI successfully reduces effort, enhances self-efficacy, and resolves interpersonal friction, making collaborative composition more fluid and accessible. However, the core tension between AI’s efficiency gains and the dilution of perceived ownership/creative identity remains a fundamental challenge for the field. Future work must prioritize interface and AI designs that actively preserve human agency, foster stylistic diversity, and enhance transparency to address these concerns, particularly for professional users. The deployment of InScoreAI <https://inscoreai.netlify.app/> and planned open-sourcing of its code provide a foundation for further exploration of AI’s evolving role in human collaboration within music and other fields.

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